

Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial studies of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes involving a bidentate Schiff base ligand

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Abstract : Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of the Schiff base derived from vanillin and 3-aminobenzoic acid were synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, conductivity, infrared, electronic, magnetic measurements and SEM. The analytical data show the composition of the metal complex to be ML₂, where L is the Schiff base ligand. The conductance data indicate that all the complexes are non-electrolytes. IR results demonstrate the bidentate binding of the Schiff base ligand involving azomethine nitrogen and carboxylato oxygen atoms. The electronic spectral measurements indicate that Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes have tetrahedral geometry, while Cu^{II} complex is square planar. The magnetic measurements show paramagnetic behaviour for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes. The SEM studies show that all the complexes are in the nanocrystalline regime. The antimicrobial activity of synthesized ligand and its complexes were screened against the bacterial species, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and the fungal species *Candida albicans*, *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Rhizoctonia bataicola* by disc diffusion method. Antimicrobial studies indicate that the metal complexes are more active than the ligand.

Keywords : Antifungal, antibacterial, Schiff base, IR, SEM.

Introduction

The metal complexes with Schiff bases as ligands have been playing an important role in the development of coordination chemistry due to their synthetic flexibility, selectivity and sensitivity towards the central metal atom, structural similarities with natural biological substances and also due to presence of imine group (-N=CH-) which imports in elucidating the mechanism of transformation and rasemination reaction in biological system¹⁻³. Furthermore, Schiff base metal complexes are being studied extensively due to their various applications such as catalysts, pharmaceutical agents, antitumor, antifungal, antibacterial, antiviral, anticonvulsive, antifouling and as corrosion inhibitors⁴. Especially, Schiff bases containing nitrogen and oxygen donor atoms play important role in biological systems and represent interesting models for metalloenzymes, which efficiently catalyze the reduction of dinitrogen and dioxygen⁵. Recently, we have synthesized and characterized some Schiff base metal complexes and their *in vitro* antimicrobial activities have been investigated⁶⁻⁸. In the present paper we report synthesis, char-

acterization and antimicrobial studies of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of Schiff base derived from vanillin and 3-aminobenzoic acid.

Results and discussion

The analytical data and physical properties of the Schiff base ligand (L) and its complexes are listed in Table 1. The Schiff base ligand was synthesized from the condensation of vanillin and 3-aminobenzoic acid. The results of elemental analysis (Table 1) of the Schiff base ligand are in good agreement with those calculated for the suggested formula (Fig. 1). The IR spectrum of the ligand showed characteristic bands due to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$ group frequencies at 1652, 1590 and 1375 cm⁻¹, respectively. The electronic spectrum of Schiff base ligand shows a broad band at 335 nm, which is assigned to π - π^* transition of the C=N chromophore. In addition, the other intense absorption bands at higher energy, 225 and 270 nm respectively, are due to the π - π^* transition of the benzene ring of the Schiff base ligand. The Schiff base ligand is soluble in common organic solvents but insoluble

Table 1. Analytical data of the Schiff base ligand and its complexes

Ligand/ Complexes	Empirical formula and colour	Calcd. (Found) (%)			Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Magnetic moment (B.M.)
		C	H	N		
L	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_4$ Yellow	66.42 (66.11)	4.83 (4.35)	5.16 (5.66)	-	-
[CoL ₂]	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8\text{CO}$ Yellowish green	60.11 (60.31)	4.04 (4.59)	4.67 (4.38)	17.0	4.80
[NiL ₂]	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8\text{Ni}$ Yellow	60.13 (60.35)	4.04 (4.21)	4.68 (4.39)	19.7	3.44
[CuL ₂]	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8\text{Cu}$ Blackish green	59.65 (59.71)	4.00 (4.25)	4.64 (4.11)	14.3	2.00
[ZnL ₂]	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8\text{Zn}$ Pale yellow	59.47 (59.49)	3.99 (4.11)	4.62 (4.23)	13.1	Dia.

Fig. 1. Proposed structure of Schiff base ligand.

in water. Refluxing a 2 : 1 molar amount of the ligand and metal salts gave the coloured complexes. All the complexes are soluble in DMF and DMSO and insoluble in other common organic solvents. The analytical data (Table 1) indicate that the metal to ligand ratio is 1 : 2 for all the complex systems. The molar conductance of all the complexes was measured in DMSO using 10^{-3} M solutions at room temperature. The low molar conductance data (Table 1) showed them to be non-electrolytes⁹.

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectrum of the free Schiff base ligand exhibits a broad band centered at 1652 cm^{-1} , due to azomethine group $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$. On complexation this band was shifted to lower frequency in the $\sim 1649\text{--}1645 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range indicating the coordination of the azomethine nitrogen atom to the metal ion. For the free ligand, the observed bands at 1590 and 1375 cm^{-1} can be respectively ascribed to asymmetric carboxyl $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$ and symmetric carboxyl $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$ groups¹⁰. During complexation they were shifted to lower frequency by $\sim 5\text{--}10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the linkage between the metal ion and carboxylato oxygen atom. The large difference between the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$ ($\sim 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicates the monodentate binding nature

of the carboxylato group¹¹ in the complexes. In the lower frequency region the new weak bands observed at $500\text{--}510$ and $433\text{--}438 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been assigned to the $\nu(\text{M}\text{--}\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}\text{--}\text{N})$ vibrations¹⁰, respectively.

Electronic spectra and magnetic properties :

The electronic spectral data of the ligand and its complexes are given in Table 2. The electronic spectrum of tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes is reported to have only one

Table 2. Electronic spectral data of the Schiff base ligand and its complexes

Ligand/ Complexes	Band assignments	Wavelength (nm)	Geometry
L	-	225, 270, 335	-
[CoL ₂]	${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$	695	Tetrahedral
[NiL ₂]	${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$	684	Tetrahedral
[CuL ₂]	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$	600	Square planar

absorption band in the visible region, due to ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transition in the range $600\text{--}700 \text{ nm}$. The other transition ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$ occurs in the IR region¹². The spectrum of present Co^{II} complex has only one band in the visible region at 695 nm . This indicates tetrahedral geometry for the complex. Generally, tetrahedral Ni^{II} complexes show an intense absorption band at $\sim 666 \text{ nm}$, due to the transition ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ ¹². The present Ni^{II} complex shows an absorption band at 684 nm . This supports the tetrahedral orientation of donor centers around the metal ion. In general, due to Jahn-Teller distortion, square planar Cu^{II} complexes give a broad absorption between 500 and 700 nm due to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transition. The electronic spectrum of the present Cu^{II} complex ex-

hibits a broad band centered at 600 nm, indicating its square planar geometry¹². The Co^{II} complex has a magnetic moment of 4.80 B.M., which is in agreement with the reported value for tetrahedral Co^{II} complex¹³. Generally, square planar Ni^{II} complexes are diamagnetic while tetrahedral complexes have moments in the range 3.2–4.1 B.M.¹³. The Ni^{II} complex reported herein has a room temperature magnetic moment value of 3.44 B.M., which is within the normal range observed for tetrahedral Ni^{II} complex. The magnetic moment value of the Cu^{II} complex was observed to be 2.00 B.M., which indicates that the complex is monomeric¹³.

Based on the results obtained from elemental analysis, conductance, infrared, electronic and magnetic moment studies, the probable structure of the complexes under investigation are given in Fig. 2.

SEM :

The scanning electron micrographs of the metal complexes are shown in Fig. 3. The SEM picture of Co^{II} complex shows agglomerated morphological structure and the presence of small grains in non-uniform size. The particle size of the above complex is in the diameter range of 1 μ m. Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes show similar type morphology with platelet-like structures, whereas Cu^{II} complex has closely packed agglomerated morphology and the particles are uniformly arranged. Again, the Cu^{II} complex showed an average particle size of less than 1 μ m, smaller than that of other complexes. The average grain size found from SEM shows that the complexes are polycrystalline with nanosized grains.

In vitro antifungal activity :

The *in vitro* antifungal activity of the Schiff base ligand,

M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}

M = Cu^{II}

Fig. 2. Proposed structure of Schiff base metal complexes.

Fig. 3. SEM images of Schiff base metal complexes : (a) Co^{II}, (b) Ni^{II}, (c) Cu^{II} and (d) Zn^{II}.

its complexes and Nystatin (as a standard compound) were tested against the fungal species *C. albicans*, *R. stolonifer*, *A. flavus*, *A. niger* and *R. bataicola*. The results of the *in vitro* antifungal screening of the synthesized ligand and its complexes are presented in Table 3(a). The results revealed that complexes are more microbial toxic than the ligand. The Co^{II} complex was found to be highly active towards *A. niger* (MIC 52 µg/mL) than other fungal species (MIC > 100 µg/mL). A good effectiveness is exhibited by Cu^{II} complex, which acts in the range 40–60 µg/mL towards *R. stolonifer*, *A. flavus* and *R. bataicola*.

The complexes Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} have moderate activity in comparison with *A. flavus* and *A. niger* (MIC 75–100 µg/mL) and less activity in comparison with *C. albicans*, *R. bataicola* and *R. stolonifer* (MIC > 100 µg/mL).

In vitro antibacterial activity :

The *in vitro* antibacterial activities of Schiff base (L) and its metal complexes were investigated against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *P. vulgaris* and *P. aeruginosa* as bacteria. The results (Table 3(b)) were compared with those of the standard drug chloroamphenicol. The free Schiff base ligand exhibit less activity

Table 3(a). Minimum inhibitory concentration of the synthesised compounds against the growth of fungi (µg/mL)

Compd.	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>R. stolonifer</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>R. bataicola</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
L	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
[CoL ₂]	52	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
[NiL ₂]	85	> 100	75	> 100	> 100
[CuL ₂]	> 100	46	50	44	> 100
[ZnL ₂]	90	> 100	80	> 100	> 100
Nystatin ^a	10	16	8	12	14

^aStandard.

Table 3(b). Minimum inhibitory concentration of the synthesized compounds against the growth of bacteria ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
L	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	95
[CoL ₂]	> 100	> 100	65	> 100	50
[NiL ₂]	> 100	35	> 100	> 100	> 100
[CuL ₂]	> 100	28	25	40	60
[ZnL ₂]	> 100	138	46	> 100	48
Chloroamphenicol ^a	4	8	10	6	12

^aStandard.

against most of the bacteria (MIC > 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), while a significant inhibitory activity, higher than that of the corresponding ligand is displayed by some of complexes (MIC < 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). In particular, the Cu^{II} complex proves to be a wide spectrum agent, showing an interesting inhibition of the growth of all Gram-positive/negative bacteria (MIC 25–60 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) except *E. coli*. In contrast, a selective effect is observed for Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes against *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris*, respectively. Ni^{II} complex exhibit a strong inhibition of the growth of *K. pneumoniae* at the concentration of 35 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. All the tested compounds are inactive against Gram-negative *E. coli* (MIC > 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$).

The remarkable activity of the Schiff base (L) complexes may arise from the uncoordinated hydroxyl and methoxy groups, which can play an important role in the antimicrobial activity. Moreover, the presence of imine group imports in elucidating the mechanism of transformation reaction in biological systems¹⁴. The results indicate that the complexes show more activity and the ligand do not have or less activity against same microorganism under identical experimental conditions. This would suggest that the chelation could facilitate the ability of a complex to cross a cell membrane and can be explained by Tweedy's chelation theory¹⁵. In addition, other factors viz. stability constant, molar conductivity, solubility, and magnetic moment are also responsible for increasing the antimicrobial activity of the complexes¹⁶.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Vanillin and 3-aminobenzoic acid were respectively obtained from Fluka and Lancaster. Metal(II) chlorides were purchased from Merck. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Solvents were purified and dis-

tilled before use. The metal content in the complexes was determined by EDTA titration. Elemental analysis was obtained using a Perkin-Elmer elemental analyzer. Conductivity measurements were made on freshly prepared 10⁻³ M solutions in DMSO at room temperature with a coronation digital conductivity meter. The IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets on a JASCO FT/IR-410 spectrometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda-25 UV/Vis spectrometer. The room temperature magnetic measurements were carried out using Guoy balance and the diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constant. SEM images were recorded in a Hitachi SEM analyzer.

Synthesis of Schiff base ligand :

To a solution of 3-aminobenzoic acid (0.2742 g, 2 mmol) in methanol, vanillin (0.3043 g, 2 mmol) in methanol was added dropwise. The above mixture was magnetically stirred for about 1 h. The solvent was evaporated and cooled at room temperature, when yellow crystals were separated out. It was washed with alcohol, ether and recrystallized from ethanol (yield : 72%).

Synthesis of metal Schiff base complexes :

Metal(II) chloride (1 mmol) was dissolved in MeOH and the solution was filtered and added dropwise into methanolic solution of Schiff base ligand (2 mmol). The above mixture was magnetically stirred and refluxed for 1 h. The metal complexes obtained were filtered, washed with MeOH and dried *in vacuo* (yield : 70–79%).

In vitro antimicrobial activity :

The Schiff base ligand and its complexes were tested against the bacterial species; *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *P. vulgaris* and *P. aeruginosa*, and the fungal species; *C. albicans*, *R. stolonifer*, *A. flavus*, *A. niger* and *R. bataicola*. These studies were carried out using

Kirby Bayer Disc diffusion method¹⁷. The test solutions were prepared in DMSO. Chloroamphenicol was used as the standard antibacterial agent whereas Nystatin was used as the standard antifungal agent. The test organisms were grown on nutrient agar medium in petri plates. The compounds were prepared in DMSO and soaked in filter paper disc of 5 mm diameter and 1 mm thickness. The discs were placed on the previously seeded plates and incubated at 37 °C and the diameter of inhibition zone around each disc was measured after 24 h for bacterial and 72 h for fungal species¹⁸. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined by serial dilution technique.

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